

VISCOSITY OF POLY-2-VINYLPYRIDINE IN ACETIC ACID

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Viscosities of poly-2-vinylpyridine have been measured in glacial and aqueous acetic acid media. The reduced viscosity *versus* concentration graphs are typical of a polyelectrolyte. Addition of pyridine, sodium acetate and barium acetate decreases the viscosity. Even small amounts of water exert considerable influence on the viscosity and thereby introduce uncertain factors in the observed results.

Poly-2-vinylpyridine has been found to exhibit polyelectrolytic properties in nitromethane (Cashin, *J. Coll. Sci.*, 1951, 6, 271) due to the weakly acidic properties of this solvent which enhance the base strength of the polymer. The present paper reports the results of viscosity measurements of poly-2-vinylpyridine in acetic acid in which the polymer is found to exhibit the essential characteristics of a polyelectrolyte. This is perhaps not surprising in view of the fact that in a strongly acidic solvent like acetic acid, the polymer base should be present to a great extent as its salt, polyvinylpyridinium acetate, which by ionisation could logically be expected to behave as a polyelectrolyte. An essentially similar phenomenon has also been observed with solutions of polyamides in formic acid (Schaeffgen and Trivisonno, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4580; 1952, 74, 2715).

EXPERIMENTAL

Two samples (A & B) of poly-2-vinylpyridine were used in the present work. These samples were obtained by bulk polymerisation at room temperature and were purified by dissolving in methylethyl ketone and precipitating with petroleum ether (Maclay and Fuoss, *J. Poly. Sci.*, 1951, 6, 511). The process was repeated thrice and the brown precipitate finally obtained was dried. A standard solution of this polymer in glacial acetic acid was made in a well-stoppered flask. Measurements were done with this solution with necessary dilution. Two such stock solutions were made with samples A and B respectively.

Materials.—99.5% Acetic acid was distilled using a long fractionating column and the central fraction was collected. A highly purified sample was obtained by freezing the acid sample three times and collecting about 200 c.c. out of one litre of the original sample. Fused sodium acetate was purified by melting and was preserved in well-stoppered bottles. Pyridine was dried over sodium hydroxide beads and then distilled, the central fraction being collected. Barium acetate was prepared by treating pure barium hydroxide with excess of acetic acid and evaporating to dryness. The concentrations of stock solutions of sodium acetate and of pyridine in acetic acid were checked by titration with standard HClO_4 in the same solvent, using methyl violet as indicator. Conductivity water was used for all the measurements.

Measurements.—All viscosity measurements were done at $35^\circ (\pm 0.01^\circ)$ with two Ostwald viscometers with flow times of 330 and 480 seconds respectively with glacial acetic acid.

TABLE I
Viscosities of poly-2-vinylpyridine.

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	η_{sp}/C in		Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	η_{sp}/C in	
	Gl. acetic acid Sample A.	Gl. acetic acid + 0.3% Ac_2O .		Gl. acetic acid. Sample B.	Gl. acetic acid + 0.3% Ac_2O .
0.10	11.75	7.90	0.10	18.89	10.40*
0.05	11.35	9.30	0.07	17.90	...
0.03	12.50	11.10	0.05	17.50	11.70
0.02	13.35	12.00	0.03	19.00	...
0.01	15.90	14.70	0.02	22.30	14.40
0.005	20.10	...	0.01	26.20	15.90
		...	0.005	...	20.10
		...	0.002	...	39.20

Conductance measurements were done at 35° with a direct reading bridge of the philosophic type using cell voltage of 2.0 at 1000 cycles per second. The conductivity cell used had a cell constant of 0.2288.

TABLE II
Conductance in glacial acetic acid.

Conc.	Sp. conductance, Sample B.	Eqv. conductance.
0.470 g./100 c.c.	24.88×10^{-6} mho	55.62×10^{-2} mho
0.313	17.35	58.17
0.202	12.33	63.77
0.135	8.86	69.04
0.090	6.05	71.16
0.060	4.34	76.01

TABLE III
Effect of water on viscosity.

Conc.	η_{sp}/C in acetic acid + added water.		
	5% H_2O Sample B ₄	10% H_2O .	20% H_2O .
0.10 g./100 c.c.	17.85	16.70	14.80
0.07	...	16.18	14.10
0.05	17.27	...	...
0.04	...	14.60	13.05
0.03	16.50	14.16	12.90
0.02	...	13.80	12.35
0.01	17.19	13.50	11.75
0.005	17.13	13.90	11.70
0.002	16.30	14.44	11.90

Characterisation of the Samples.—The molecular weights of the polymer samples were determined by osmotic pressure measurements in dimethylformamide and found to be 2,20,000 for sample A and 2,88,000 for B.

The equivalent weight of the polymer base B was determined by potentiometric titration in phenol-chloroform solution with $N/25$ HCl in propyleneglycol-chloroform. Glacial acetic acid could not be used as a titration medium since the salt formed in

course of the titration separated out in the form of a rubbery precipitate. The equivalent weight, determined as above, was found to be about 110 as compared with the theoretical value of 105 for vinylpyridine. If we rule out the possibility of the presence of any spurious impurity in the polymer sample, the high value of the observed equivalent weight may be taken to indicate that roughly 5% of the pyridine groups in the chain have become inert with regard to basic character, presumably as a result of atmospheric oxidation. The brown colour of the sample perhaps lends some support to this conclusion. No further purification of the samples was, however, attempted.

DISCUSSION

Viscosities in Acetic Acid and Polyelectrolytic Nature of the Polymer.—Viscosities of samples A and B were measured in glacial acetic acid at polymer concentrations in the range of 0.01-0.1 g./100 c.c.

FIG. 1

Viscosity of samples A and B in acetic acid.

1. Sample A in acetic acid.
2. Sample B in acetic acid.
3. (1) + 0.3% Ac₂O.
4. (2) + Do.

though the degree of dissociation is naturally very small. In a medium of such a low

Results are presented in Table I and graphs of reduced viscosities *versus* polymer concentrations are shown in Fig. 1 (curves 1 and 2). It will be seen that the curves are not linear as in the case of neutral polymers, but show a sharp rise at the dilute end and are reminiscent of polyelectrolytes. It may be mentioned in this connection that in non-acidic solvents like chloroform, alcohol, methylethyl ketone, etc., polyvinylpyridine exhibits normal viscometric character.

That polyvinylpyridine does exist as an electrolyte in acetic acid solution, was confirmed by conductance measurements on sample B over the concentration range of 0.06-0.47 g./100 c.c. The results are represented in Table II. If the equivalent conductance is plotted against the square root of the concentration, the nature of the curve obtained is found to be essentially similar to that for a weak electrolyte in water or any electrolyte in glacial acetic acid medium (Kolthoff and Willman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1014). The curve does not provide any specific information about the nature of the ionic species in solution and, hence, is not shown here. But the results definitely indicate that the polymer base does give rise to ions in solution,

dielectric constant, the magnitude of interionic forces should, however, be very great despite a very low concentration of free ions. Thus, the repulsion between the positively charged centres on the polymer chain, though sparsely distributed thereon, will be of sufficient magnitude to cause it to exhibit the characteristic properties of a typical polyelectrolyte. Moreover, intermolecular, apart from intramolecular, electrostatic forces may be expected to play an important role in a medium of low dielectric constant. In relatively concentrated solutions of the polymer, intermolecular repulsive forces between charged centres should tend to inhibit the dilatation of the polymer coils, and these forces naturally become less significant on dilution of the polymer solution, resulting in a rise in viscosity at high dilution.

FIG. 2
Viscosity of sample B in
aq. acetic acid.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively
to 5%, 10% and 20% water.

FIG. 3
Viscosity of sample B in presence
of NaAc and pyridine.

Conc. of NaAc (N) : (1) $2.44 \cdot 10 \times 10^{-4}$; (2) 24.4×10^{-4} ; (3) 0.228
Conc. of pyridine (N) : (4) 2.53×10^{-4} ; (5) 25.3×10^{-4} ; (6) 0.316.

It ought to be emphasised at this stage, however, that the whole idea as to the polyelectrolytic nature of the compound will be justified only if the polymer is mole-

cularly dispersed in solution. Unfortunately, it has not been possible to establish this point, since osmotic pressure method could not be applied. It should also be borne in mind that the electroviscous effect (Smoluchowski, *Kolloid Z.*, 1916, 18, 190) might play a relatively important role in a medium of such low dielectric constant, this effect being superimposed on the folding-unfolding phenomenon as exhibited by the polyelectrolyte. From the general trend of the results, however, especially with regard to the effect of added acetates on the viscosity (reported below), it would be quite reasonable to conclude that poly-2-vinylpyridine essentially behaves as a typical polyelectrolyte in acetic acid solutions.

Viscosities in presence of Added Water.—The viscosities of sample B were measured in acetic acid containing 5, 10 and 20% water by volume respectively. The reduced viscosity is found to be progressively lowered by increasing the water content of the medium (Fig. 2 and Table III). This may arise from an increase in acetate ion concentration on addition of water, which represses the viscosity of the polyelectrolyte just as the addition of counter-ions would be expected to do in the case of any polyelectrolyte. To eliminate the effect of small amounts of water in the solvent, if any, about 0.3% acetic anhydride was added to the glacial acetic acid and viscosities of samples A and B were measured in this as the solvent. Results are shown in Table I. The reduced viscosity *versus* concentration curve for this solvent (curves 3 and 4, Fig. 1) was found to be lower than that obtained with glacial acetic acid without added anhydride. It is very likely, therefore, that the presence of traces of water in acetic acid raises the viscosity, but on further increasing the concentrations of water, the viscosity falls. It will be further observed from Fig. 1 that for glacial acetic acid, the curves 1 and 2 have a tendency to pass through minima in the region of intermediate concentrations of the polymer, and in this respect closely resemble the curves obtained by Schaeffgen and Trivisonno (*loc. cit.*) with polyamides in 99.5% formic acid. On addition of 0.3% acetic anhydride, however, the minimum is found to disappear (Fig. 1, curves 3 and 4).

Viscosities in presence of Added Counter-ions.—Viscosities of sample A were measured in presence of various concentrations of pyridine and sodium acetate (Tables IV and V). Some representative data are indicated in Fig. 3. The reduced viscosities are lowered by the addition of counter-ions and go on decreasing as the acetate concentration is increased. Thus, the counter-ions here act in the same manner as in the cases of other polyelectrolytes, *i. e.*, they lower the viscosity as a result of the lowering of the degree of dissociation of the polyelectrolyte.

At any particular concentration of pyridine or sodium acetate, the reduced viscosity slowly increases on decreasing polymer concentration, passes through a maximum, decreases thereafter and rises again on further dilution. The nature of the curves is rather different from those obtained with polyelectrolytes in general, and the appearance of a minimum in the dilute end of the curve is difficult to explain on the basis of the current theory of polyelectrolytes. The apparent anomaly might, however, arise from traces of water present in the acetic acid used as the solvent.

TABLE IV

Effect of pyridine on viscosity.

Conc. (g./100c.c.)	η_{sp}/C (0.3165).	Sample A.			
		in presence of pyridine*. (0.0633).	in presence of pyridine*. (0.0127).	in presence of pyridine*. (0.00253).	in presence of pyridine*. (0.00025).
0.10	3.90	3.97	4.80	6.57	8.80
0.07	4.02	4.16	4.63	...	...
0.05	4.06	4.74	4.86	6.50	9.75
0.04	4.20	...	...	...	...
0.035	...	5.01	...	...	...
0.03	4.26	4.87	5.00	6.70	10.75
0.02	4.27	6.34	6.32	6.20	10.15
0.01	4.29	9.02	8.67	6.50	9.76
0.005	...	14.50	13.57	7.45	10.58
0.002	...	...	...	...	14.50

* The concentrations (g. equiv./litre) of pyridine are shown in parenthesis at the heads of the respective column

TABLE V

Effect of sodium acetate on viscosity.

Conc. of polymer. (g./100 c.c.)	η_{sp}/C (0.228).	Sample A.			
		in presence of sodium acetate*. (0.0244).	in presence of sodium acetate*. (0.0122).	in presence of sodium acetate*. (0.00244).*	in presence of sodium acetate*. (0.00024).
0.10	3.44	4.45	4.40	6.92	9.80
0.05	3.60	4.20	...	7.13	10.16
0.04	...	...	...	7.20	10.60
0.03	...	4.07	4.68	7.22	11.39
0.02	3.44	3.90	4.61	6.95	11.15
0.015	...	...	...	...	10.60
0.010	3.30	4.10	4.75	6.65	10.91
0.007	...	...	5.75	...	...
0.005	3.50	5.80	6.95	7.03	12.00
0.002	3.40	...	8.60	8.40	14.40

* The concentrations (g. equiv./litre) of sodium acetate are given in parenthesis at the heads of the respective column.

To eliminate water as far as practicable, a highly purified sample of acetic acid was prepared by repeated freezing. The viscosities of sample B were measured in this freshly prepared solvent in presence of sodium and barium acetates. The results are shown in Fig. 4.

FIG. 4

Viscosity of sample B in presence of NaAc and BaAc.

- (1) $2.44 \times 10^{-4} N$ -NaAc. (2) $1.56 \times 10^{-4} N$ -BaAc.
 (3) $1.56 \times 10^{-4} N$ -BaAc + 0.1% water.
 (4) 0.227N-NaAc. (5) 0.172N-BaAc.

The graphs (Fig. 4) exhibit the normal features as usually obtained with polyelectrolytes in presence of added counter-ions. At concentrations 2.44×10^{-4} g. eq./litre of sodium acetate and 1.56×10^{-4} g. eq./litre of barium acetate the graphs (curves 1 and 2) show the expected maxima and at higher concentrations of acetate (0.227 g. eq./litre of sodium acetate and 0.172 g. eq./litre of barium acetate) the graphs become linear (curves 4 and 5), indicating that the polyelectrolyte character of the polymer has been completely suppressed. To test the effect of traces of water, viscosities were measured in presence of 1.56×10^{-4} g. eq./litre of barium acetate in acetic acid containing 0.1% added water. The reduced viscosities (curve 3) were found to be appreciably affected by the addition of even this small amount of water, as would be seen by comparing curves 2 and 3 in Fig. 4. The apparent anomalies presented by some of the data reported above presumably arise from the presence of traces of water in the acetic acid used as the solvent, which introduce uncertain factors in the observed results. This makes a thorough interpretation of the viscosity data rather difficult, unless experiments are carried out under absolutely anhydrous conditions.

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